

D3: Standardized metadata catalogue for environmental, satellite and health data available.

Reporting for Project:	MetaMap ³	Date	13.01.2023 (Version 1.1)
Work package:	3	Partner:	HMGU
Deliverable:	3	Authors:	Marco Dallavalle

Introduction

In the MetaMap³ project, three centers (HMGU, UFZ, and DLR) bring together exemplary metadata of domain health, environment and earth observation, and conceptualize a mapping strategy for the linkage of the metadata of different domains.

The aim of deliverable D3 is to transfer the use case metadata into a common schema and set up a standardized metadata catalogue to host environmental, satellite and health metadata of the project partners. The implementation in deliverable D3 is based on the conceptual work of deliverable D2. In deliverable D2 we selected ISO 19115¹ as standard and GeoNetwork² as platform. In Deliverable 3, we report on the installation of a test instance of GeoNetwork and on the uploading of our metadata use cases.

Metadata catalog

GeoNetwork² is a catalog application designed to store spatially referenced resources. It includes metadata editing and search functions as well as an interactive web map viewer. A GeoNetwork instance is hosted on a SLES virtual machine at HMGU. The catalog is installed with docker. Currently, the catalog is behind a firewall. Our catalog is only accessible by the MetaMap³ partners at: epirudb1.helmholtz-muenchen.de:8080/geonetwork/srv/ger/catalog.search#/home.

Individual logins are set up and we are testing the full functionality of the platform. Currently only registered user can explore the metadata records. However, it is possible to publish selected resources so that any user can view the public metadata without credentials. To allow the general user to explore the metadata catalog two steps are required: adjust the firewall rules and have the catalog administrator set a metadata record to public. As far as the functionalities of the catalog are concerned, the filter settings can be customized using a source editor. The source editor allows to drop or add search criteria, which will be shown in the browser to the user. At the time of writing, it is possible to filter the metadata records based on the spatial representation type (grid/vector), keywords, organizations, spatial extent and other criteria.

Figure 1 and 2 show a visual representation of our instance of the catalog after logging in. The records can be browsed thematically. Records of the children cohorts GINI and LISA³ (HMGU), drought monitor^{4,5} (UFZ) and land cover⁶ (DLR) have been entered into the catalog. For each record, an XML file has been uploaded to the catalog. Additionally, GeoNetwork allows editing a metadata entry on the fly.

Figure 3 and 4 present two screenshot of the land cover metadata uploaded to the catalog by DLR. The record includes a link to the DLR web map service (WMS). It is possible to load the land cover map into the web map viewer of GeoNetwork. The metadata can be downloaded as XML. Figure 5 shows the drought monitor metadata uploaded by UFZ. In the catalog, the map of the drought monitor is animated.

Figure 6 depicts the metadata of the GINIplus COVID-19 questionnaire. The metadata of the questionnaire are aggregated based on the Maelstrom categories⁷ and included into a GeoPackage (GPKG) file as attribute table. The spatial research data is not included in the catalog and cannot be loaded into the web map viewer. In order to add the spatial file we would have to set up a WMS and, for a given entry, add a link in the metadata.

Summary

Deliverable 3 focused on the practical implementation of the strategy developed in Deliverable 2. We set up an instance of GeoNetwork on a server at HMGU. Currently, we are populating a MetaMap³ instance of the catalog with our metadata use cases. At least one entry for each domain has been uploaded.

We intent to include metadata concerning the participants distribution to the children cohorts GINI and LISA³ without exposing sensitive information about participants' data. Figure 7 and 8 show the participants for the 20 years follow-up on a 5 km INSPIRE grid.

Figure 1. Visual representation of the catalog after logging in at the time of writing.

Figure 2. Catalog list page.

The screenshot shows the MetaMap catalog interface. On the left, there are several filter sections:

- Type of resources:** Dataset (3) [checked], Service (1) [unchecked]
- Spatial representation type:** Grid (1) [unchecked], Vector (1) [unchecked]
- Available in:** Download service [unchecked], View service (1) [unchecked]
- Keywords:** Germany (2) [unchecked], Opendata (2) [unchecked], Land cover (1) [unchecked], Land cover map (1) [unchecked], Sentinel-2 (1) [unchecked], Soil Moisture Index (1) [unchecked], Birth cohort (1) [unchecked], Covid-19 (1) [unchecked], Epidemiology (1) [unchecked], Questionnaire (1) [unchecked]
- Scales:** [collapse icon]
- Years:** [collapse icon]
- Organizations:** German Aerospace Center (DLR) (1) [unchecked], Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (1) [unchecked]

The main area displays three resource cards:

- SMI total soil monthly 1951-01 - 2021-12:** Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research. Status: On going.
- Land Cover DE - Sentinel-2 - Germany, 2015:** German Aerospace Center (DLR). Status: Completed.
- GINIplus COVID-19 questionnaire:** Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research. Status: On going.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the land cover⁶ metadata record provided by DLR – part 1.

The screenshot shows the metadata record for the 'Land Cover DE - Sentinel-2 - Germany, 2015' dataset. The record includes:

- Title:** Land Cover DE - Sentinel-2 - Germany, 2015
- Description:** This land cover classification of Germany was created using Sentinel-2 imagery from the years 2015 to 2017 and LUCAS 2015 in-situ reference data (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/lucas). It contains seven land cover types: (1) artificial land, (2) open soil, (3) high seasonal vegetation, (4) high perennial vegetation, (5) low seasonal vegetation, (6) low perennial vegetation and (7) water with a spatial resolution of 10m x 10m. For further information, please see the following publication: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2020.102065
- Status:** Completed
- Download and links:**
 - LCC_DE_2015:** Land Cover DE, 2015. WMS icon. Add to map button. Description: This dataset is published in the view service (WMS) available at https://geoservice.dlr.de/eoc/land/wms? with layer name LCC_DE_2015.
 - EOC Geoservice Map Context:** EOC Geoservice Map Context (de:lcc). Open link button. URL: https://geoservice.dlr.de/web/maps/de:lcc
 - HTTP Download:** HTTP Download (Land Cover DE). Open link button. URL: https://download.geoservice.dlr.de/LCC_DE/files/
 - Scientific publication:** Scientific publication describing the Land Cover DE product https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2020.102065. Open link button.
- Overview:** A large map of Germany showing the land cover classification, with a smaller thumbnail below it.
- Spatial extent:** A map showing the location of Germany within Europe, with a black box indicating the spatial extent of the dataset.
- About this resource:**
 - INSPIRE themes:** Land cover
 - Categories:** Imagery base maps earth cover
 - GEMET - INSPIRE themes, version 1.0:** Land cover

Figure 4. Screenshot of the land cover⁶ metadata record provided by DLR – part 2.

About this resource

INSPIRE themes	Land cover
Categories	Imagery base maps earth cover
GEMET - INSPIRE themes, version 1.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land cover
Keywords	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sentinel-2 Land cover map Germany Opendata
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> English
Resource identifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://geoservice.dlr.de/catalogue/srv/metadata/8205e1c9-14c3-47a7-ac12-8c890225680a
Legal constraints	<p>License</p> <p>Nutzungsbedingungen: Lizenz, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/ / Terms of use: License, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/</p> <pre>{ "id": "cc-by-nc/4.0", "name": "Creative Commons Namensnennung - Nicht kommerziell 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)", "url": "http://dcat-ap.de/def/licenses/cc-by-nc/4.0", "quelle": "Copyright DLR (year of production)" }</pre> <p>Nutzungseinschränkungen: Das DLR ist nicht haftbar für Schäden, die sich aus der Nutzung ergeben. / Use Limitations: DLR not liable for damage resulting from use.</p> <p>Nutzungsbedingungen: Lizenz, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/ / Terms of use: License, https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/</p>
Contact for the resource	<p>German Aerospace Center (DLR)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Author: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> matthias.weigand@dlr.de michael.wurm@dlr.de Point of Contact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> geoservice@dlr.de
Status	Completed

Figure 5. Screenshot of the UFZ Drought monitors⁴ metadata.

☰ SMI total soil monthly 1951-01 - 2021-12

The UFZ Drought Monitor provides daily information on drought and soil moisture throughout Germany. This information is based on simulations using the mHM meso-scale hydrological model developed at the UFZ (www.ufz.de/mhm). Updated daily, the maps show you the drought status of the soil in its entirety and the topsoil, which reacts more quickly to recent precipitation, and the water available to plants in the soil.

On going

Download and links

Scientific publication
Open link

Scientific publication describing SMI <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/11/7/074002>

About this resource

Theme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil Moisture Index
Keywords	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil Moisture Index
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English
Contact for the resource	<p>Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author, Author, Point of Contact: ✉ klima@ufz.de
Status	On going

Technical information

Metadata information

 Download metadata

🗺 Overview

📍 Spatial extent

🕒 Resource events

Figure 6. Screenshot of the metadata of the GINIplus³ COVID-19 questionnaire.

GINIplus COVID-19 questionnaire

This resource describes the spatial metadata of the Questionnaire of the COVID-19 pandemic of the GINIplus study. GINIplus is the acronym of the German Infant Study on the influence of Nutrition Intervention PLUS environmental and genetic influences on allergy development.

On going

About this resource

Categories	Health Environment
General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Birth cohort Q • Covid-19 Q • Questionnaire Q • Epidemiology Q
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English
Resource identifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identifier
Credit	GINIplus MetaMap3
Status	On going

Technical information

Representation type	Vector
Coordinate reference system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25832

Metadata information

[Download metadata](#)

Contact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leibniz-Institut für umweltmedizinische Forschung • Auf'm Hennekamp 50, Düsseldorf, 40225, Germany • Point of Contact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elke Link (Data manager) • +49 211 3389-286
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Spatial extent

Resource events

Creation
01-01-2015 02:00

Provided by

Updated:

a month ago

No ratings ★

Share on social sites

Figure 7. Distribution of the residences of GINI (top) and LISA (bottom) cohort participants.

Follow-up
20 years

Follow-up
20 years

References

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3. Heinrich J, Brüske I, Cramer C, et al. GINIplus and LISApplus – Design and selected results of two German birth cohorts about natural course of atopic diseases and their determinants. *Allergol Select.* 2017;1(1):85-95. doi:10.5414/ALX01455E
4. Zink M, Samaniego L, Kumar R, et al. The German drought monitor. *Environ Res Lett.* 2016;11(7):074002. doi:10.1088/1748-9326/11/7/074002
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6. Weigand M, Staab J, Wurm M, Taubenböck H. Spatial and semantic effects of LUCAS samples on fully automated land use/land cover classification in high-resolution Sentinel-2 data. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation.* 2020;88:102065. doi:10.1016/j.jag.2020.102065